

COMPRESSION MOULDING OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES OF GMTS AND CO-MINGLED MATERIALS FOR OPTIMISED MACRO AND MICRO MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY: To increase the usage of glass and polypropylene composites from semi-structural to structural applications, a higher and aligned glass content is needed. The co-moulding of GMTs and pre-consolidated woven co-mingled materials have been investigated to fulfill this requirement. The effects of temperature on the polypropylene were examined using gel permeation chromatography to determine preheat windows. Experimental design techniques were used to investigate the effects of processing parameters and interactions on laminates. Processing variables were ranked in order of importance for maximum flexural moduli. Statistically based processing models were generated to enable the prediction of laminate flexural moduli with varying processing conditions. Time at pressure had the greatest contribution and additional laminates were made to determine the minimum time required for full consolidation. Studies of the microstructure of the sandwich laminates were performed to investigate impregnation and removal of voidage.

KEYWORDS: co-mingled materials, glass mat thermoplastics, compression moulding, sandwich materials, voidage, experimental design techniques, gel permeation chromatography

INTRODUCTION

The major use of continuously reinforced thermoplastic composites in the automotive industry is in the production of semi-structural parts from glass mat thermoplastics (GMT). The melt impregnation of the glass mat and polypropylene in double belt laminators limits the amount of glass in standard commercial grades of GMTs to 40% by mass [1]. These materials, with typical processing cycle times of 35 seconds, offer the ability to fill large and complex moulds. GMTs are increasingly replacing steel in complex semi-structural load bearing applications, such as the VW Golf front end. In order to increase the usage of thermoplastic composites into continuously loaded structural parts the glass fibre content needs to be increased.

The glass fibre content in compression moulding materials can be increased by forming a sandwich laminate with a glass fibre fabric at the surface and a GMT core. Matrix material must impregnate the glass fibre fabric and several ways of combining fibre and matrix materials are available including co-weaving, plied matrix, inter-dispersed yarns, powder impregnation and co-mingling [2-3]. Co-mingling combines glass fibres and polypropylene filaments giving a homogeneous distribution of reinforcement and matrix, reducing the mass

transfer distance of the matrix during processing to typically 50 microns [3]. Co-mingled materials offer the potential for the manufacture of structural parts at lower moulding pressures due to the higher and aligned fibre content (compared with GMTs) and the intimate combination of reinforcement and matrix.

The complexity of components moulded from co-mingled materials is limited by geometries that the fabric will drape or conform to during processing [4]. In the sandwich laminate, flow of the GMT core between the co-mingled materials offers the potential for the production of complex geometries with a fast cycle time [5]. Co-mingled materials provide a localised higher and aligned glass fibre content and are placed locally in the tool at regions of higher operating stress. During consolidation of the sandwich laminate, the GMT core damps thickness variations between the shearing fabric but overall complexity is still thought to be restricted by the drape of the co-mingled material. Where complex features are required in the region of the co-mingled facings, the GMT has been shown to break through the co-mingled fabric to fill features such as ribs in a tool. The major difference between processing aligned materials and GMTs is that generally no bulk or large scale flow of the co-mingled structure is thought to occur.

OBJECTIVES

Given the apparent potential for increasing the use of thermoplastic composites into structural applications, assessment of the processing of material combinations was required. The specific aims of this work have been to investigate and optimise the non-isothermal compression moulding of combinations of GMTs and co-mingled fabrics and to determine the effects of processing on laminate microstructure.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials

The GMTs used consisted of a 40% by mass continuous random glass mat reinforced polypropylene, produced by melt impregnation in a double belt laminator. The co-mingled materials consisted of a balanced weave fabric of superficial density 650 g/m^2 woven from yarns of 60% by mass co-mingled E-glass and polypropylene. Laminates of 300mm were produced from two GMT blanks, 171 x 171mm, sandwiched between 2 blanks of co-mingled material, 198 x 198 mm, to give a nominal thickness of 4mm, as shown in Fig. 1. The co-mingled material blanks comprised two layers of co-mingled fabric which were supplied consolidated to a thickness of 0.92mm.

Figure 1: Laminate cutting plan and blank locations

Processing Study

This study of the co-moulding of co-mingled materials and GMTs covered the time at moulding pressure, moulding pressure, average material pre-heat temperature, tool temperature and their interactions, as shown in Table 1. Tool temperature settings were determined from ambient to the upper range suggested by the GMT manufacturers [6]. Oven preheat temperatures were bound by the melting point and the onset of degradation of the polypropylene matrix. Moulding pressures were defined by the upper limit of the moulding press and the minimum required to fill the tool. Times at pressure were selected from recommended values of 5 seconds per mm part thickness. The maximum hydraulic press compression velocity of 12.9mm/sec was used for all experiments. Black pigmented co-mingled material and naturally pigmented GMT blanks were used to give a visual indication of flow in each laminate.

Table 1: Processing Variables

Processing Parameter	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Time at Pressure, (TP)	10 seconds	30 seconds	50 seconds
Moulding Pressure, (P)	50 bar	125 bar	200 bar
Material Temperature, (MT)	180°C	200°C	220°C
Tool Temperature, (TT)	20°C	50°C	80°C

Non-isothermal Compression Moulding Equipment

Infra red ovens are established technologies for preheating in compression moulding and thermo-forming, creating high flux levels for rapid material heating. A 4.5kW R-Royce infra red oven was used for heating the composite materials. A Bradley and Turnton 150 tonne hydraulic moulding press was used to generate maximum pressures of 200 bar on the laminate, with electrically heated platens used to heat the press tooling. Computer control of the press enabled fast material transfer from the oven to press, typically under 10 seconds, and the data acquisition of thermal histories. A steel compression moulding tool was designed and

produced with vertical telescoping shear edges. Fig. 2 shows the experimental moulding facility.

Figure 2: Hot flow compression moulding facility

Experimental Design

Experimental design was used to investigate the effects of 4 processing parameters at 3 settings. A 27 run central composite array was used, shown in Table 2, with each trial performed with levels as described in the array. The array ensured sufficient degrees of freedom to examine the linear and quadratic effects of the 4 factors together with any potential interactions in the system. Multiple linear regression (MLR) techniques were used to generate prediction equations using a second order polynomial, shown generally for two factors, A and B, in Eqn 1. The unknown parameters $\{\beta_i\}$ are the regression coefficients which were estimated by the method of least squares and the selected equation is the one for which the sum of the squares of the residuals is minimised [7].

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 A + \beta_2 B + \beta_3 A^2 + \beta_4 B^2 + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Table 2: Central Composite Design Array

Row No.	TP (sec)	P (bar)	MT (°C)	TT (°C)	Row No.	TP (sec)	P (bar)	MT (°C)	TT (°C)
1	30	125	200	50	15	50	50	220	80
2	10	50	180	20	16	10	200	220	80
3	50	50	180	20	17	50	200	220	80
4	10	200	180	20	18	30	125	200	50
5	50	200	180	20	19	10	125	200	50
6	10	50	220	20	20	50	125	200	50
7	50	50	220	20	21	30	50	200	50
8	10	200	220	20	22	30	200	200	50
9	50	200	220	20	23	30	125	180	50
10	10	50	180	80	24	30	125	220	50
11	50	50	180	80	25	30	125	200	20
12	10	200	180	80	26	30	125	200	80
13	50	200	180	80	27	30	125	200	50

Mechanical Testing

The effects of processing parameters on the sandwich region flexural moduli and strength were measured for each laminate, with results averaged along the centre line. Specimen dimensions and locations are shown in Fig. 1. Flexural tests and tensile tests were performed at 10mm/min at 5mm/min respectively.

PREHEATING FOR SANDWICH LAMINATES

Determination of Upper Processing Temperature

The high shear viscosity of polypropylene requires heating above the melt temperature to reduce the viscosity for impregnation. The onset of a thermal oxidative degradative reaction formed the maximum processing temperature for the composite under consideration. A processing window can be established as a time frame where the middle of the composite has reached the desired processing temperature but without degrading polymer at the surface. DSC trials had shown the co-mingled material polypropylene to have a reduced oxidative induction time compared with the GMT polypropylene. The effects of preheating on the weight average molar mass (Mw) of the co-mingled material polypropylene were investigated using the technique of gel permeation chromatography (GPC) to define the upper preheat thresholds for processing.

Figure 3: Effect of time and temperature on PP degradation

Samples of pre-consolidated co-mingled material were heated to oven temperatures of 180°C to 240°C in 10°C steps for 7 time intervals at each temperature. Fig. 3 shows the relations between time and temperature effects on the weight average molar mass (Mw). For temperatures of 240°C, 230°C, 220°C and 210 °C Mw reduced with an increasing time at temperature with the effect increasing with higher temperatures. For temperatures of 180°C, 190°C, 200 °C the material was stable for preheat times exceeding 600 seconds. A line at 175,500 representing the onset of degradation determined a maximum preheat time for each temperature. At the highest oven temperature of 230°C used for the sandwich laminates, the co-mingled material preheat time of 145 seconds was within the onset of degradation at 200 seconds.

Combination Material Preheating

Three average material temperatures were used to investigate effects on the consolidation of the composite. Therefore three heating profiles were determined for both composites to reach the desired processing temperature simultaneously. Co-mingled materials and GMTs have different fibre and matrix architectures resulting in disparate heat transfer characteristics. Separate studies of GMTs and pre-consolidated co-mingled materials were used to identify overlaps in processing windows. Additional experiments were used to verify and tune these predictions. The GMT was placed into the oven first and the co-mingled material added towards the end of the heating cycle. Materials were heated separately and stacked together before transfer to the tool. Table 3 summaries the preheat parameters for the three average material temperatures used in the main processing study, with Fig. 3 showing the disparate heating times.

Figure 4: Preheat curves for sandwich laminates

Table 3: Combination Preheat Cycles

Oven Temp, (°C)	Average Temp, (°C)	Material	Time, (sec)
190	180	GMT	0 to 560
		Co-mingled	420 to 560
210	200	GMT	0 to 550
		Co-mingled	430 to 550
230	220	GMT	0 to 460
		Co-mingled	315 to 460

PROCESS OPTIMISATION

The 27 laminates were produced and flexural moduli were measured. Using MLR, regression coefficients were calculated with a quadratic approximation fitted to moduli data and a linear fit to the six possible interaction effects. The t ratios were calculated similarly in a spreadsheet

and used to quantify the magnitude and significance of the effect of each factor on the moduli. The percentage contributions from each significant linear factor, quadratic factor or interaction effect on the flexural moduli are shown in Table 4 (Insignificant factors labelled as '*'). Eqn 2 gives the prediction equation, where coefficients for insignificant interactions and factors were excluded.

Table 4: Processing Contributions, (%), on Flexural Moduli at 95% Confidence

Linear Effects				Quadratic Effects				Linear Interaction Effects						
TP	P	MT	TT	TP ²	P ²	MT ²	TT ²	TPxP	TPxMT	TPxTT	PxTT	MTxTT	PxMT	ε
17	11	*	15	15	10	*	*	*	*	9	*	*	9	14

$$Response = 11.2 + 0.3 TP + 0.2 P + 0.3 MT - 0.6 TP^2 + 0.5 P^2 + 0.2 TPxTT + 0.2 PxMT \quad (2)$$

To reduce error in the analysis, the levels of the four processing parameters were scaled between -1 and +1 to give a linear spacing of the original factor levels [7]. Any level of scaled processing parameter inside the range investigated can be substituted into Eqn 2 to give laminate moduli at those processing conditions.

Partial differentiation and solution of the processing equations gave maximum values for the processing factors for each laminate property. Consideration of these results with the other mechanical test data for the specimens shown in Fig. 1 resulted in optimum conditions of: a time at pressure of 50 seconds, a pressure of 200 bar, a material temperature of 220°C and a tool temperature of 80°C. Eqn 2 was utilised to generate processing response curves to show the effect of varying two variables, while the other variables were kept at the maximum level, on the

laminate flexural moduli. The domination of linear effects and exclusion of insignificant factors, without the reaching of maximum points, limited the validity of the processing models to the upper and lower levels of the processing study. Fig. 5 shows the effects of: firstly, moulding pressure and time at moulding pressure and secondly, tool temperature and material preheat temperature, on flexural moduli.

Fig. 5: Effect of Pressure and Temperature on Sandwich Laminate Flexural Modulii

Verification of Process Models and Optimum Processing Conditions

Laminates were produced at the optimised processing conditions described above. Mean and maximum moduli of 11.5 GPa and 12.5 GPa resulted. The processing model predicted moduli of 12.3 GPa at optimum conditions. Confidence limits were calculated using the upper and lower 95% limits for the significant regression coefficients which were substituted into Eqn 2, giving 13.2 GPa and 11.4 GPa respectively. The laminates produced at the optimised conditions have therefore confirmed the predictions at optimised levels.

Time at Pressure

Increasing the time at pressure from 10 to 50 seconds showed the largest effect on the laminate moduli. To investigate the effects of time at pressure further, 6 laminates were produced at optimised conditions with times at pressure of 5, 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 seconds. Laminate mechanical properties were measured, as shown in Fig. 6, and the through thickness microstructure examined.

Figure 6: Effect of time at pressure on E_{Flex}

DISCUSSION

Time at Pressure

Increasing the time at pressure showed the largest effect on laminates with properties increasing with time. Through thickness micrographs of laminates produced at 10, 30 and 50 seconds of compression time are compared in Fig. 7. These show the GMT region between the co-mingled material outer layers. An increased time at pressure decreased void contents with the thickness of the mid plane void layer reducing faster in the GMT region at the laminate periphery. It was necessary to maintain the pressure to reduce the void content and to stabilise the laminate until the matrix temperature had reduced to below the onset of polypropylene crystallisation.

Figure 7: Effect of time at pressure on centre line microstructure

The non-isothermal compression moulding of GMT results in fountain flow through the tool cavity. The GMT freezes to the cold steel surface as it flows across the tool, with the core flowing between the cooling outer layers. With sandwich laminates, the previously consolidated co-mingled material blanks again freeze to the steel tool surface with the rapid cooling due to the higher glass content and lack of insulating air in the material structure. Fountain flow of the GMT core then results between the insulating layers of co-mingled material rather than steel, reducing the rate of heat transfer from the GMT core to the tool. The viscosity of the GMT core would therefore remain low enough for material to flow for longer time periods. In the sandwich laminate the void content, at 30 seconds compression time, of the GMT core in the sandwich region was higher than that at the laminate periphery, composed entirely of GMT. Increased time at pressure, compared with a GMT laminate, was therefore required to reduce void content in the sandwich region.

Moulding Pressure

Fig. 5 shows that increased pressure above 90 bar increased flexural moduli. The laminate mid-plane was well consolidated at 50 and 200 bar, but with increased voidage in the co-mingled material at the laminate surfaces at 50 bar. This was removed at 200 bar, as shown in a through thickness micrograph in Fig. 8 of the surface region of a laminate made at optimum conditions.

Material Preheat Temperature

An average preheat temperature of 220°C increased laminate moduli, as shown in Fig.5. A decrease in properties would result if the materials were heated to higher temperatures where the bulk of the matrix material would degrade. At preheat temperatures of 180°C the co-mingled material on the tensile face of the specimen delaminated from the GMT core during testing.

Comparison of the micrographs in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, at 220°C and 180°C respectively, showed large areas of voidage between the glass fibres in the co-mingled material at 180°C. The increased voidage in the co-mingled material with reduced temperatures showed the importance of a rapid transfer of the hot blanks from the oven to the tool. Excessive transfer

times would reduce the material temperature, increasing the polypropylene viscosity, and the co-mingled material would not consolidate fully.

Tool Temperature

The processing model plot in Fig. 5 showed increased flexural moduli as the tool temperature increased. Voidage occurred between the co-mingled material glass tows adjacent to the tool surface at 20°C tool temperature. The number of voids in the co-mingled layers decreased towards the mid-plane of the laminate. An increased tool temperature reduced the rate of cooling of the material adjacent to the tool surface, improving the surface finish and increasing flash on laminates. Decreased cooling, reducing the rate of viscosity increase, enabled the full impregnation of the co-mingled material glass fibres to occur.

Interaction Effects

Significant interactions occurred between: firstly, time at pressure and tool temperature and secondly, pressure and material temperature. At higher times at pressure, increased tool temperatures resulted in a greater stiffness increase than at reduced times. Increased tool temperatures improved impregnation of the co-mingled blanks adjacent to the tool surface. Increased times at pressure were required to reduce voidage, which decreased mechanical properties, from the mid-plane of the laminate. At higher pressures, increased material temperatures increased moduli while at lower pressures a reduction in moduli occurred.

Processing Observations

During the compression moulding of sandwich structures, the flow of the GMT blank to the periphery of the tool was observed to drag the black pigmented polypropylene of the co-mingled materials. At optimised processing conditions this reached 28mm, indicating good mixing of the two polypropylenes. The co-mingled material blanks remained where placed in the tool.

Figure 8: Surface microstructure at optimum processing conditions

Figure 9: Surface microstructure at 180°C material preheat temperature

CONCLUSIONS

Optimum processing parameters for the production of sandwich laminates have been predicted and verified. Pressure should be maintained to eliminate mid-plane voidage. Maximum material preheat temperatures reduced matrix viscosities for impregnation of the co-mingled material glass fibres. An increased tool temperature assisted impregnation of the co-mingled materials provided that the required time at pressure was maintained. The flexural moduli were increased by 104% compared with properties for GMT laminates and were 86% of properties for co-mingled materials, for equivalent thicknesses. Substantial increases in load carrying ability resulted from the combination of the two material forms, while still offering the ability to flow the GMT between the co-mingled material blanks to fill the tool. Study of the interface of the co-mingled material and GMT regions showed that the glass fibres in the GMT moved with the flowing matrix, eliminating interlaminar voids and matrix rich areas.

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